

Exploring nonlinear wave mixing with a mass–spring simulator

Marco P. M. de Souza^{a)}

Grupo de Pesquisa Estrutura da Matéria e Física Computacional, Universidade Federal de Rondônia, Campus Ji-Paraná, Rondônia, Brazil

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We investigate nonlinear wave-mixing processes using a classical nonlinear mass-spring oscillator driven by one or two external periodic forces. By introducing quadratic and cubic nonlinear terms in the restoring force, we establish a direct analogy between the oscillator dynamics and second- and third-order nonlinear optical phenomena. Using Fourier-domain arguments, we show how the nonlinear terms couple different spectral components and generate new frequencies through processes analogous to second-harmonic generation, optical rectification, sum- and difference-frequency generation, third-harmonic generation, and four-wave mixing. Numerical simulations were performed with an interactive simulator from the SimuFísica platform using a fourth-order Runge-Kutta algorithm. The results reveal the emergence of harmonic generation, beat frequencies, DC components, four-wave-mixing sidebands, cascaded spectral generation, and frequency-comb-like structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear optics studies phenomena associated with the propagation of intense electromagnetic radiation in material media, where the optical response of the medium ceases to be proportional to the incident electric field. Since the development of the first lasers in the 1960s, sufficiently intense electromagnetic fields have enabled the observation of several nonlinear processes, including harmonic generation, optical rectification, and four-wave mixing (FWM). These phenomena have applications in several areas of physics and engineering, including spectroscopy, optical telecommunications, precision metrology, and optical frequency-comb generation.

One of the best-known classical descriptions of the interaction between radiation and matter is the Lorentz model, in which electrons bound to atoms are treated as damped harmonic oscillators driven by an oscillating electric field⁶. In this model, the electron dynamics exhibits a strong mathematical analogy with that of a classical mass–spring system subjected to a periodic external force. The introduction of nonlinear terms in the restoring force allows one to qualitatively describe several phenomena typical of nonlinear optics, establishing a conceptual connection between classical mechanical systems and optical frequency-mixing processes.

This analogy has been explored in several works devoted to the teaching or description of nonlinear optical phenomena using classical mass–spring systems^{1,4}. In particular, some studies have related the optical phenomenon known as electromagnetically induced transparency (EIT)² to coupled oscillators, as well as extensions involving double EIT³.

In this work, we investigate the dynamics of a nonlinear mass–spring oscillator subjected to the simultaneous action of two sinusoidal external forces, emphasizing its connection with wave-mixing processes in nonlinear

optics. We use an interactive computational simulator from the SimuFísica platform to numerically investigate harmonic generation, frequency mixing, and frequency-comb-like spectral structures.

Beyond its connection with contemporary nonlinear-optics phenomena, the approach presented here has pedagogical potential for advanced undergraduate and introductory graduate courses in electromagnetism, optics, nonlinear dynamics, and computational modeling. Concepts such as harmonic generation, four-wave mixing, and optical frequency combs are often introduced through abstract expansions of nonlinear susceptibilities and frequency-domain formalisms. The analogy with a mass–spring oscillator allows these processes to be visualized in a familiar mechanical system, facilitating the connection between the temporal evolution of the oscillator and its frequency-domain response.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II, we present the theoretical model of the nonlinear oscillator and discuss the origin of the spectral components generated by the quadratic and cubic restoring-force terms. In Sec. III, we present numerical examples obtained with the simulator, including processes analogous to second-harmonic generation and four-wave mixing. Finally, in Sec. IV, we present the conclusions of this work.

II. NONLINEAR OSCILLATOR MODEL

We begin with the classical Lorentz model for electrons bound to atoms⁶, in which the electron–nucleus interaction is approximated by a harmonic restoring force:

$$F_{binding} = -kx = -m\omega_0^2x, \quad (1)$$

where m is the electron mass, x represents its displacement relative to the equilibrium position, k is the effective restoring-force constant, and ω_0 is the natural oscillation frequency of the system. To account for dissipative mechanisms, a phenomenological damping term is also introduced:

^{a)}Electronic mail: marcopolo@unir.br

$$F_{damping} = -\gamma \frac{dx}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

where γ is the damping coefficient. The incident electromagnetic wave is assumed to have the form

$$E(t) = E_0 \cos(\omega_1 t), \quad (3)$$

with amplitude E_0 and angular frequency ω_1 .

The collective response of the medium to the incident radiation is described by the electric polarization P , defined as the induced electric dipole moment per unit volume:

$$P(t) = -Nex(t), \quad (4)$$

where e is the magnitude of the electron charge and N is the atomic density. From the relationship between P and the electronic displacement x , one obtains the well-known linear response

$$P(t) = \epsilon_0 \chi E(t), \quad (5)$$

where ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity and χ is the electric susceptibility of the medium.

Equation (5) shows that, in the linear regime, the polarization oscillates at the same frequency as the applied electric field. Microscopically, this means that the induced atomic dipoles execute harmonic oscillations driven by the incident electromagnetic wave. Since accelerated charges emit electromagnetic radiation, the oscillating electrons re-radiate electromagnetic fields at the same frequency as the external excitation. The coherent superposition of the radiation emitted by all dipoles in the material gives rise to the electromagnetic wave emitted by the medium, characterizing the linear optical response of the system.

The development of high-intensity coherent sources made experimentally accessible regimes in which the optical response of materials becomes nonlinear. Under these conditions, nonlinear contributions to the polarization can no longer be neglected, giving rise to characteristic nonlinear-optical phenomena such as harmonic generation, frequency mixing, and optical rectification.

Processes such as second-harmonic generation, in which the medium emits radiation at twice the incident frequency, can only be described when the electric polarization is written as a power-series expansion of the electric field⁵:

$$P(t) = \epsilon_0 \left[\chi^{(1)} E(t) + \chi^{(2)} E^2(t) + \chi^{(3)} E^3(t) + \dots \right], \quad (6)$$

where $\chi^{(1)}$ corresponds to the linear susceptibility introduced in Eq. (5), while $\chi^{(2)}$ and $\chi^{(3)}$ are the second-

and third-order nonlinear susceptibilities, respectively. In general, higher-order susceptibilities are much smaller than the linear contribution, so their effects become significant only in regimes of sufficiently intense electric fields.

A. The nonlinear model

Our model consists of a nonlinear mass-spring oscillator subjected to the simultaneous action of two sinusoidal external forces. In analogy with the nonlinear expansion of the electric polarization introduced in Eq. (6), we generalize the restoring force of the spring by including quadratic and cubic nonlinear terms:

$$F_{el} = -kx - k_2 x^2 - k_3 x^3, \quad (7)$$

where k is the linear spring constant, while k_2 and k_3 characterize the nonlinear contributions to the restoring force. The quadratic term breaks the inversion symmetry of the elastic force, analogously to what occurs in nonlinear optical media with nonvanishing second-order susceptibility⁵.

The external forces are assumed to have the form

$$F_i(t) = F_i \cos(\omega_i t), \quad (8)$$

where F_i and ω_i represent the amplitude and angular frequency of the i th external excitation, respectively. Figure 1 illustrates the analogy between the mechanical system considered here and a nonlinear optical medium driven by two monochromatic electromagnetic fields.

Starting from Newton's second law and including a phenomenological damping term proportional to the velocity, we obtain the differential equation governing the system dynamics:

$$m\ddot{x} + \gamma\dot{x} + kx + k_2 x^2 + k_3 x^3 = F_1(t) + F_2(t). \quad (9)$$

The presence of nonlinear terms causes different spectral components of the motion to become coupled, allowing new frequencies to be generated from the frequencies of the external forces. In the following subsections, we separately analyze the cases dominated by the quadratic and cubic nonlinearities, emphasizing their connection with frequency-mixing processes in nonlinear optics.

B. Frequency mixing induced by the quadratic term

Let us first consider the case in which only the quadratic nonlinearity is present:

$$m\ddot{x} + \gamma\dot{x} + kx + k_2 x^2 = F_1 \cos(\omega_1 t) + F_2 \cos(\omega_2 t). \quad (10)$$

FIG. 1. (a) Illustration of the model: a classical anharmonic oscillator subjected to bichromatic excitation. (b) Optical analog: two lasers incident on a nonlinear medium, generating new radiation associated with the polarization P .

Although approximate perturbative solutions can be obtained for this equation⁵, exact analytical solutions are generally not available. To understand the origin of the frequencies generated by the nonlinearity, it is particularly convenient to analyze the system in the frequency domain.

We write the mass position in terms of its inverse Fourier transform:

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{x}(\omega) e^{-i\omega t} d\omega, \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{x}(\omega)$ represents the Fourier transform of $x(t)$. The time derivatives become

$$\dot{x}(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (-i\omega) \tilde{x}(\omega) e^{-i\omega t} d\omega, \quad (12)$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (-\omega^2) \tilde{x}(\omega) e^{-i\omega t} d\omega. \quad (13)$$

Using the exponential representation of the driving terms,

$$\cos(\omega_j t) = \frac{1}{2} (e^{i\omega_j t} + e^{-i\omega_j t}), \quad (14)$$

and substituting the previous expressions into Eq. (10), we obtain, in the frequency domain,

$$D(\omega) \tilde{x}(\omega) + \frac{k_2}{m} \widetilde{x^2}(\omega) = \frac{\pi F_1}{m} [\delta(\omega - \omega_1) + \delta(\omega + \omega_1)] + \frac{\pi F_2}{m} [\delta(\omega - \omega_2) + \delta(\omega + \omega_2)], \quad (15)$$

where we define

$$D(\omega) = -\omega^2 - i\frac{\gamma}{m}\omega + \frac{k}{m}. \quad (16)$$

The nonlinear term involves the Fourier transform of $x^2(t)$, given by the convolution⁹

$$\widetilde{x^2}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{x}(\omega') \tilde{x}(\omega - \omega') d\omega', \quad (17)$$

that is, $\widetilde{x^2} = \tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{x}$. While the linear term $D(\omega) \tilde{x}(\omega)$ acts independently on each spectral component, the convolution introduces coupling between different frequencies of the system.

Within the linear approximation, the oscillator response is expected to contain only the frequencies of the external forces:

$$\tilde{x}(\omega) \sim a_1 \delta(\omega - \omega_1) + a_1^* \delta(\omega + \omega_1) + a_2 \delta(\omega - \omega_2) + a_2^* \delta(\omega + \omega_2). \quad (18)$$

Substituting these spectral components into the convolution of Eq. (17), we observe that new frequencies are generated through the sum and difference of the original frequencies. For example, the combination of the ω_1 component $[a_1 \delta(\omega - \omega_1)]$ with itself produces

$$\widetilde{x^2}(\omega) \propto \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(\omega' - \omega_1) \delta(\omega - \omega' - \omega_1) d\omega', \quad (19)$$

which imposes $\omega = 2\omega_1$. A spectral component therefore emerges at twice the fundamental frequency, corresponding to the second harmonic. It is worth noting that while representing the monochromatic response in terms of Dirac delta functions is mathematically convenient, it represents an idealization of a steady-state regime. Physically, the presence of the damping coefficient γ ensures

that the spectral components possess a finite linewidth [Lorentzian profiles associated with $1/|D(\omega)|^2$ from Eq. (16)]. The use of strict delta functions here is understood as the limiting case of weak damping, acting as a mathematical scaffold to identify the coupled frequencies without dealing with the cumbersome algebra of finite linewidths.

Similarly, cross terms involving ω_1 and ω_2 produce components at

$$\omega = \omega_1 + \omega_2 \quad (20)$$

and

$$\omega = \omega_1 - \omega_2, \quad (21)$$

corresponding, respectively, to sum- and difference-frequency generation processes.

$$D(\omega)\tilde{x}(\omega) + \frac{k_3}{m}\widetilde{x^3}(\omega) = \frac{\pi F_1}{m} [\delta(\omega - \omega_1) + \delta(\omega + \omega_1)] + \frac{\pi F_2}{m} [\delta(\omega - \omega_2) + \delta(\omega + \omega_2)], \quad (24)$$

where

$$\widetilde{x^3}(\omega) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{x}(\omega') \tilde{x}(\omega'') \tilde{x}(\omega - \omega' - \omega'') d\omega' d\omega'', \quad (25)$$

represents a triple convolution, $\widetilde{x^3} = \tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{x}$. Unlike the quadratic case, in which pairs of spectral components are coupled, the cubic term mixes triplets of spectral components.

Assuming again that the linear response contains only the frequencies of the external forces,

$$\tilde{x}(\omega) \sim a_1 \delta(\omega - \omega_1) + a_1^* \delta(\omega + \omega_1) + a_2 \delta(\omega - \omega_2) + a_2^* \delta(\omega + \omega_2), \quad (26)$$

we observe that the triple convolution produces spectral components of the form

$$\omega = \pm\omega_a \pm \omega_b \pm \omega_c, \quad (27)$$

where ω_a , ω_b , and ω_c can take the values ω_1 or ω_2 . Examples include

$$3\omega_1 = \omega_1 + \omega_1 + \omega_1, \quad (28)$$

$$2\omega_1 - \omega_2 = \omega_1 + \omega_1 + (-\omega_2), \quad (29)$$

$$2\omega_2 - \omega_1 = \omega_2 + \omega_2 + (-\omega_1). \quad (30)$$

Since the generated frequencies may themselves participate again in the convolution process, the resulting spectrum eventually contains integer linear combinations of the fundamental frequencies:

$$\omega = n\omega_1 + m\omega_2, \quad n, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (22)$$

C. Frequency mixing induced by the cubic term

Let us now consider the case in which only the cubic nonlinearity is present:

$$m\ddot{x} + \gamma\dot{x} + kx + k_3x^3 = F_1 \cos(\omega_1 t) + F_2 \cos(\omega_2 t), \quad (23)$$

corresponding to a Duffing-type equation^{7,8} subjected to bichromatic excitation. In the frequency domain, the equation becomes

These components correspond, respectively, to third-harmonic generation and to the characteristic sidebands of four-wave mixing. As in the quadratic case, successive nonlinear interactions lead to cascaded spectral generation. In a system with purely cubic nonlinearity, the resulting frequencies can be written as

$$\omega = n\omega_1 + m\omega_2, \quad |n| + |m| = 1, 3, 5, \dots \quad (31)$$

indicating that only odd-order combinations of the fundamental frequencies are generated.

Table I summarizes some representative nonlinear frequency-generation processes and their corresponding terminology in nonlinear optics.

III. EXAMPLES

In this section, we present examples of the dynamics of the nonlinear forced mass-spring oscillator subjected to one or two external driving forces. The cases discussed here were solved numerically using the Mass-Spring System simulator (Fig. 2) available on the SimuFísica platform¹⁰⁻¹². The numerical algorithm employed in the simulator is based on the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method¹⁵.

TABLE I. Examples of nonlinear frequency-generation processes discussed in this work and their optical analogs.

Process	Generated frequency	Nonlinear optics terminology
$\omega_1 + \omega_1$	$2\omega_1$	Second-harmonic generation (SHG)
$\omega_1 - \omega_1$	0	Optical rectification (OR)
$\omega_1 + \omega_2$	$\omega_1 + \omega_2$	Sum-frequency generation (SFG)
$\omega_1 - \omega_2$	$\omega_1 - \omega_2$	Difference-frequency generation (DFG)
$\omega_1 + \omega_1 + \omega_1$	$3\omega_1$	Third-harmonic generation (THG)
$2\omega_1 - \omega_2$	$2\omega_1 - \omega_2$	Four-wave mixing (FWM)
$2\omega_2 - \omega_1$	$2\omega_2 - \omega_1$	Four-wave mixing (FWM)

FIG. 2. Graphical interface of the Mass-Spring System simulator (version 1.13) used to investigate the cases discussed in this work. Access link: <https://simufisica.com/en/spring-mass/>.

A. Second-harmonic generation

In nonlinear optics, second-harmonic generation is a second-order process in which the medium absorbs two photons with frequency ω_1 and emits a photon with frequency $2\omega_1$. This process has several technological applications, including laser frequency conversion, nonlinear microscopy, and the generation of radiation in spectral regions that are difficult to access directly.

In Fig. 3, we present a numerical example dominated by the quadratic nonlinearity, that is, with $k_3 = 0$. We consider $k_2 = k/100 = 0.9 \text{ N/m}^2$ and only one external force, $F_1(t)$ ($F_2 = 0$), oscillating with amplitude $F_1 = 100 \text{ N}$ and angular frequency $\omega_1 = 4 \text{ rad/s}$. The remaining parameters are $\gamma = 1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, $m = 10 \text{ kg}$, and $k = 90 \text{ N/m}$, such that the natural frequency of the system is $\omega_0 = 3 \text{ rad/s}$. The system therefore operates outside the resonance condition.

As initial conditions, we assume that the mass is initially at rest at the equilibrium position at $t = 0$. Fig-

ure 3(a) shows the temporal evolution of the position $x(t)$ of the mass. An initial transient regime associated with the damped natural response of the oscillator is observed. After approximately $t \approx 70 \text{ s}$, the dynamics becomes dominated by the forced periodic response.

Figure 3(b) presents a zoom of the temporal evolution in the interval $t \in [0, 32] \text{ s}$. In this region, a clear amplitude modulation associated with the beat phenomenon¹⁴ can be observed, with beat frequency given by $\omega_1 - \omega_0 = 1 \text{ rad/s}$. This behavior arises from the interference between the natural response of the oscillator, near ω_0 , and the external driving frequency ω_1 .

Figure 3(c) shows the Fourier transform of $x(t)$ considering the entire temporal evolution, $t \in [0, 300] \text{ s}$ (dashed curve), and also only the stationary regime after removing the initial transient ($t \in [70, 300] \text{ s}$, solid curve). In the dashed curve, two main spectral components are observed: the external driving frequency and the damped natural frequency of the oscillator, close to ω_0 . When the transient regime is removed, the response becomes dominated by the component associated with the external

FIG. 3. Dynamics of the nonlinear mass–spring system and its spectral components. (a) Temporal evolution of the mass position x . (b) Zoom of the temporal evolution in the interval $t \in [0, 32]$ s. (c) Fourier transform of x with (dashed curve) and without (solid curve) the transient regime. (d) Zoom of the Fourier transform. (e) Schematic representation of the optical/quantum analog of second-harmonic generation. Parameters used: $m = 10$ kg, $k = 90$ N/m, $\gamma = 1$ kg·s⁻¹, $k_2 = 0.9$ N/m², $k_3 = 0$, $F_1 = 100$ N, $\omega_1 = 4$ rad/s, and $F_2 = 0$. Access link for this case: <https://simufisica.com/95KQ3B>.

excitation.

A zoom of the Fourier spectrum is shown in Fig. 3(d), revealing additional spectral components of the system. At $\omega = 8$ rad/s, a clear second-harmonic component appears at $2\omega_1$. The beat frequency $\omega_1 - \omega_0$ is also present, disappearing after the transient regime is removed. In addition, a DC component appears at $\omega = 0$, as predicted in Sec. II B. In the context of nonlinear optics, this component is associated with optical rectification, in which the nonlinear response of the medium produces a static polarization and, consequently, a DC electric field. The interpretation of second-harmonic generation in terms of photons is illustrated in Fig. 3(e).

When the mass–spring oscillator enters resonance with the external force, the signatures of second-harmonic generation and the analog of optical rectification become more pronounced. In Fig. 4, we present the results obtained under the same conditions as in Fig. 3, except that now $\omega_1 = \omega_0 = 3$ rad/s.

The DC component of the oscillation can be directly observed in Fig. 4(a) through the asymmetry between maxima and minima after the transient regime (see

dashed line), and also in Fig. 4(b), where the relative amplitude of the Fourier component at $\omega = 0$ becomes significantly larger. Figure 4(c), displayed on a semilogarithmic scale, also reveals the presence of the third harmonic.

Figure 4(d) presents a photon-based interpretation of the weak spectral component at $3\omega_1$. Although the quadratic term directly generates only second-order processes, successive nonlinear interactions also produce this higher-order harmonic.

B. Four-wave mixing

In nonlinear optics, four-wave mixing is a third-order process in which different spectral components interact through the cubic susceptibility $\chi^{(3)}$ of the medium. In its simplest form, two photons associated with one frequency combine with a photon at another frequency, generating sidebands such as $2\omega_1 - \omega_2$ and $2\omega_2 - \omega_1$. This mechanism plays an important role in phenomena such as parametric amplification, frequency conversion, and

FIG. 4. Dynamics of the nonlinear mass–spring system and its spectral components under resonance conditions. (a) Temporal evolution of the mass position x . (b) Fourier transform of x . (c) Fourier transform on a semilogarithmic scale. (d) Schematic representation of the optical/quantum analog of third-harmonic generation. Parameters used: the same as in Fig. 3, except that $\omega_1 = \omega_0 = 3$ rad/s. Access link for this case: <https://simufisica.com/8PI2fF>.

optical frequency-comb generation.

In Fig. 5, we present the simulation results for the case in which $k_2 = 0$ and $k_3 = k/100 = 0.9$ N/m³. Two external forces are considered, with amplitudes $F_1 = F_2 = 50$ N and angular frequencies $\omega_1 = 2.9$ rad/s and $\omega_2 = 3.1$ rad/s. The remaining parameters and initial conditions are the same as those used in Figs. 3 and 4, such that the natural frequency of the system remains $\omega_0 = 3$ rad/s.

Figure 5(a) shows the Fourier transform of the position $x(t)$, while Fig. 5(b) presents a zoom in the region $\omega \in [2.2, 4.4]$ rad/s. Several frequencies associated with third-order nonlinear processes can be observed. In particular, the frequencies

$$2\omega_1 - \omega_2 = 2.7 \text{ rad/s} \quad (32)$$

and

$$2\omega_2 - \omega_1 = 3.3 \text{ rad/s}, \quad (33)$$

corresponding to the characteristic sidebands of four-

wave mixing, are clearly visible and schematically represented in Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), respectively.

Once formed, the modes at 2.7 and 3.3 rad/s may participate in further nonlinear interactions, giving rise to additional frequencies through cascade processes. One example is the component

$$3\omega_2 - 2\omega_1 = 3.5 \text{ rad/s}, \quad (34)$$

illustrated in Fig. 5(e).

Figure 5(b) also reveals a comb-like spectral structure composed of approximately equally spaced modes separated by the difference between the driving frequencies,

$$\omega_2 - \omega_1 = 0.2 \text{ rad/s}. \quad (35)$$

This behavior is analogous to the formation of optical frequency combs produced by cascaded four-wave-mixing processes¹³.

In addition to the main FWM sidebands around the driving frequencies, a weaker spectral structure emerges

FIG. 5. Dynamics of the nonlinear mass–spring system with $k_3 \neq 0$ and two external forces. (a) Fourier transform of x . Inset: zoom in the region $\omega \in [7.7, 11.1]$ rad/s. (b) Zoom of (a) in the region $\omega \in [2.1, 4.4]$ rad/s. (c), (d), and (e) represent optical/quantum analogs of some of the oscillation frequencies present in (b). Parameters used: the same as in Fig. 3, except that $\omega_1 = 2.9$ rad/s, $\omega_2 = 3.1$ rad/s, $F_1 = F_2 = 50$ N, $k_2 = 0$, and $k_3 = 0.9$ N/m³. Access link for this case: <https://simufisica.com/9DmLd4>.

near the third-harmonic region, extending approximately from 8.1 to 10.9 rad/s, as shown in the inset of Fig. 5(a). These peaks are associated with third-order nonlinear processes involving components such as

$$3\omega_1, \quad (36)$$

$$2\omega_1 + \omega_2, \quad (37)$$

$$\omega_1 + 2\omega_2, \quad (38)$$

and

$$3\omega_2, \quad (39)$$

in addition to higher-order cascaded interactions. While the terms $3\omega_1$ and $3\omega_2$ correspond to third-harmonic generation, the intermediate mixed frequencies result from sum-frequency processes associated with the cubic nonlinearity.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we investigated the dynamics of a nonlinear mass–spring oscillator driven by two external periodic forces and explored its connection with nonlinear optical wave-mixing processes. By introducing quadratic and cubic nonlinear terms in the restoring force, we showed that the oscillator generates new spectral components through frequency mixing mechanisms directly analogous to second- and third-order nonlinear optical phenomena.

Using Fourier-domain arguments, we demonstrated how the quadratic nonlinearity produces second-order

processes such as second-harmonic generation, optical rectification, sum-frequency generation, and difference-frequency generation. Likewise, the cubic nonlinearity was shown to generate third-order processes, including third-harmonic generation and four-wave mixing sidebands. The repeated action of these nonlinear mixing mechanisms leads naturally to cascaded spectral generation and to the emergence of frequency-comb-like structures.

The numerical simulations obtained with the interactive SimuFísica mass-spring simulator reproduced the spectral signatures predicted by the theoretical model. In particular, the simulations revealed the appearance of harmonic generation, sidebands associated with four-wave mixing, beat frequencies, DC components, and cascaded nonlinear spectral structures. The results also illustrated the importance of resonance conditions and transient dynamics in the observed spectra.

Beyond the specific nonlinear processes investigated here, the model provides an accessible classical framework for discussing fundamental concepts of nonlinear optics using a mechanical analogy familiar to undergraduate students. The direct visualization of the oscillator motion and its Fourier spectrum offers an intuitive way to connect nonlinear differential equations, spectral analysis, and wave-mixing phenomena. In this sense, the simulator may serve as a useful pedagogical tool in courses on oscillations and introductory nonlinear optics.

V. DATA

The datasets generated during this work are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20487214>.

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